

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE UN'S RECOMMENDATIONS ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR THE MEDIA

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Abstract: One of the rapidly developing technological innovations that has entered various areas of our lives and activities is artificial intelligence. We can say that artificial intelligence, which is at the forefront due to its speed of spread, impact, as well as the number of threats and problems it creates or may create, not only opens up wide opportunities during its activities, but also requires a serious view and approach to risks. This study analyzes the UN's view of artificial intelligence as a global management tool, its activities related to regulating it, especially the documents prepared by UNESCO. The main research problem is whether artificial intelligence is effective in adapting to global regulation. In addition to the use of artificial intelligence as a technological tool in the era of the information society, predictions and assumptions about the future of its management functions are included in the study. During the research, in addition to the documents and approaches mentioned above, information and reports published on the official website of the UN on artificial intelligence, as well as the activities of the expert commission on artificial intelligence were analyzed. As a result of the research, issues arising from the UN's activities on artificial intelligence, discussions on global ethical standards, ethical principles when using artificial intelligence, points such as human rights, risks related to the spread of disinformation and the increase in cases of information manipulation were assessed and recommendations were put forward. The main ideas obtained in the end are related to the UN's intention that artificial intelligence should be evaluated and regulated not only as a technological tool, but also within the framework of ethical, legal and social responsibility. In addition, the UN also puts forward ideas regarding the effectiveness of using artificial intelligence to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals it has put forward.

Keywords: UN, UNESCO, artificial intelligence, technology, sustainable development.

In recent years, the rapid development of artificial intelligence technologies has led to serious transformations in the media sector. The application of artificial intelligence tools in processes such as news preparation, dissemination, audience analysis and content personalization has become widespread. Against the background of these changes, international organizations, in particular the United Nations, have put forward a number of recommendations and principles to regulate the ethical, legal and social aspects of artificial intelligence. The UN's advice on artificial intelligence is of great importance for the media in terms of both opportunities and responsibilities.

Another important issue that the UN's advice on artificial intelligence focuses on is the prevention of disinformation.

Artificial intelligence-generated fake images, videos and texts (deepfake technologies) increase the risk of spreading misinformation in the media. In this context, the UN recommends that media organizations implement technological mechanisms for

identifying materials created using artificial intelligence and strengthen fact-checking processes. This approach is of particular importance in terms of ensuring information security and protecting public opinion from manipulation. In particular, artificial intelligence can play the role of an important technological tool to achieve the goals aimed at solving problems such as education, health, climate change, etc.

These activities or recommendations of the UN regarding artificial intelligence undoubtedly play an important role for the media. In particular, the media encounters more ethical and legal problems related to the use of artificial intelligence. Considering all this, the points we have highlighted above are very important in terms of assessing the current situation and reducing or preventing risks.

The UN recommendations also aim to eliminate bias in artificial intelligence algorithms. Algorithms used on media platforms can produce results that can lead to discrimination against certain social groups. For example, the dominance of certain topics or views during the personalization of news feeds can negatively affect information diversity. The UN recommends that media organizations ensure the transparency of algorithms, explain the principles of their operation and conduct regular audits. These measures contribute to the balanced and objective presentation of media content.

Another important aspect of the UN's advice on artificial intelligence for the media is related to the maintenance of professional standards. Although artificial intelligence makes the work of journalists easier, the importance of the human factor does not diminish. The UN considers it important for journalists to adhere to ethical norms, verify content created by artificial intelligence, and maintain editorial responsibility. This approach plays an important role in maintaining the quality of journalism and preventing the weakening of professional standards.

In addition, the UN supports the inclusive development of artificial intelligence technologies. In the media sector, this means expanding access to information resources for various social groups. Artificial intelligence technologies create opportunities such as automatic subtitles, audio reading and translation for people with disabilities. By promoting the development of such technologies, the UN contributes to making the media more accessible and inclusive. This serves to ensure information equality. The UN recommendations on artificial intelligence also influence the formation of legal regulations in the media sector. Many countries take the UN principles as a basis when developing legislation on artificial intelligence. This creates conditions for the formation of uniform standards at the global level and the introduction of responsible innovations in the media environment. In particular, issues such as copyright, responsibility allocation and ethical frameworks for content created by artificial intelligence can be regulated more clearly on the basis of these recommendations.

Consequently, the UN's recommendations on artificial intelligence provide important directions for ensuring safe, ethical and responsible activities in the media sector. These recommendations enable the media to effectively use technological opportunities while at the same time maintaining their social responsibility to society. As more widespread application of artificial intelligence technologies is expected in the future, the application of the principles established by the UN by the media will be of particular importance in terms of the stability of the information environment, the protection of public trust and the development of democratic values.

References:

1. UNESCO. Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence. – Paris: UNESCO, 2021.
2. UNESCO. Guidance for Generative AI in Education and Research. – Paris: UNESCO, 2023.
3. International Telecommunication Union. AI for Good Global Summit Report. – Geneva: ITU, 2023.
4. <https://www.un.org/en/global-issues/artificial-intelligence>
5. The United Nations. Artificial intelligence and human rights. [https://www.globalcompact.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Dokumente PDFs/artificial intelligence and human rights EN.pdf](https://www.globalcompact.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Dokumente_PDFs/artificial_intelligence_and_human_rights_EN.pdf)
6. <https://2021-2025.state.gov/risk-management-profile-for-ai-and-human-rights/>
7. [https://reports.weforum.org/docs/WEF Artificial Intelligence in Media Entertainment and Sport 2025.pdf](https://reports.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Artificial_Intelligence_in_Media_Entertainment_and_Sport_2025.pdf)